

“FRAMES TO THE NEWS” AND “SPIRALS OF SILENCE”

International Case Studies of Linear Movement and Circulation of News
Between News Agencies, Mass Media Outlets, and Interest Groups as their
Framework

Marcos de Noticias y Espirales del Silencio

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ABSTRACT

A general inhomogeneity of news agencies marks the discrepancy between definitions of a news agency, the function of news agencies, and the closeness of news agencies to other news outlets among the mass media. Different cases give evidence that these differences exist in internationally operating news agencies. We argue with two claims accessing the contemporary situation: a) we rely on the perspective of classic analysis of the sender and receiver(s) of a message in a communication model and b) special interest groups as connected segments of subnetworks in the mass media industry. We will examine several worldwide operating news agencies with internet presence regarding their self-description, their role in mass media communication, and classic definitions of news agencies. After examining several cases, we will show the general common roles of news agencies in the mass media network. The variety of news agencies results in differentiated forms of these distributors. While major news agencies work as contributors of information for other mass media and thus technically fulfill the role of a news agency, smaller agencies have the declared aim to cover 'special interest' serving as a counterpoint to mainstream news agencies. News agencies participate in linear and circular distribution forms we classify here as 'frames of the news' and 'spirals of silence'. Our examination shows that news agencies as producing and delivering organizations for the mass media work with high self-reference and reference to other mass media.

KEY WORDS: news agencies, mass media industry, worldwide operating news agencies, internet, distribution forms, 'frames of the news' and 'spirals of silence'

RESUMEN

Las nuevas agencias marcan diferencias entre definiciones y funciones del mundo de las agencias de noticias sobre todo en el ámbito internacional. Existe la perspectiva tradicional del emisor y receptor, y la perspectiva de los intereses de grupos en subredes dentro de la industria de los medios. Se examinan casos de operaciones mundiales a través de internet. Luego se presentan los roles comunes de nuevas agencias. Las nuevas agencias participan en la distribución lineal y circular de noticias en lo que hemos denominado "esquema de noticias y espiral del silencio" con una alta autoreferenciación.

Palabras Clave: Nuevas agencias, industria de los mass medias, agencias de cobertura mundial, internet, formas de distribución, "esquema del silencio".

DEFINITIONS AND RESEARCH OF NEWS AGENCIES AS CONTRIBUTOR IN MASS COMMUNICATION

In an answer to the question ‘How to spread the news?’ news agencies as institutionalized distributors must be mentioned. But asking how they act and whether news agencies operate in the same manner under common conditions of globalization, the answer needs our awareness of distinguished roles of several types of news agencies. Studying specific cases we see how news agencies as parts of networks serve as links to other organizations and interest groups in a formal framework of mass media. We conclude showing how news agencies serve as frames deciding in a process of preselection about their form, contents, structure, and availability.

A news agency (wire service or news service) is by definition an organization of journalists established to supply news reports to organizations in the news trade such as newspapers, magazines, and radio and television broadcasters. News agencies prepare hard news stories and feature articles that can be used by other news organizations. The *UNESCO Institute of Statistics* published the *Questionnaire on Newspaper Statistics*. The objective of this *Questionnaire on Newspaper Statistics* was to survey recent trends in selected areas of the newspaper industry across its member states.¹ According to the UNESCO a news agency has the following definition: “A news agency collects information and news for the media and delivers it electronically. It can supply news for example in the form of texts, graphics, videos, and pictures to media organizations and websites around the world. A news agency can be a national agency for news within a country, or a foreign news agency for international news.”² However, this definition doesn’t cover all recently established types of news agencies. Reference works on news agencies exist, but don’t cover all types of agencies.³

While mass media research highlights the mass media outlets and their specific types and forms, less research exists for the delivering organizations like news agencies. Nevertheless, news agencies play an important rule for the distribution of news. Several accounts have been put forward by researchers

¹ 2005 - Questionnaire on Newspaper Statistics. Unesco Institute of Statistics. Retrieved June 26, 2007. <[Http://www.uis.unesco.org/ev.php?ID=5831_201&ID2=DO_TOPIC](http://www.uis.unesco.org/ev.php?ID=5831_201&ID2=DO_TOPIC)>

² 2005 - Questionnaire on Newspaper Statistics. Unesco Institute of Statistics. Retrieved June 26, 2007. <[Http://www.uis.unesco.org/ev.php?ID=5831_201&ID2=DO_TOPIC](http://www.uis.unesco.org/ev.php?ID=5831_201&ID2=DO_TOPIC)>

³ As a general diacronic study we must mention:

Shrivastava, K. M. *News Agencies from Pigeon to Internet*. Elgin, Ill.: New Dawn Press, 2007

Single studies are:

Harris, Phil. *Reporting Southern Africa: Western News Agencies Reporting from Southern Africa*. Paris: Unesco, 1981

Joch Robinson, Gertrude. *News Agencies and World News*. Fribourg/Switzerland: Univ. Press 1981

interested in specific forms of news agencies, but none of them has developed a theory of the structure of news agencies and their role in the mass media. They offer rules for their functions, but many of them are synchronic and study specific times and special events reflected in mass media. Less research has been made regarding the new forms of journalism provided on the internet. Sample cases dominate the research about news agencies.⁴ The basic types of news agencies are known; but both critical awareness and research of the above mentioned interference between journalism, marketing, and PR lacks. Especially the change of online news presentations makes it necessary to investigate into their latest developments.

Following Peterson and McLendon "using mass communication theory" their study analyzes "press coverage of an appropriations conflict between two nationally prominent universities. Its purpose was to decide whether newspapers give preferential treatment to their local universities, ultimately producing bias in their coverage of higher education."⁵ Hughes and Lawson stated that in Mexico "the relationship between media ownership and partisan bias has been an important source of controversy in emerging democracies. Systematic tests of the effects of ownership, however, remain relatively rare."⁶ They came to the conclusion "that changes in ownership patterns are unlikely to eradicate partisan bias, and we discuss other institutional remedies aimed at insulating both private and state-run media from political manipulation."⁷ Other studies are interested in the efficiency of international mass media in the process of democratization. For example Oates and Roselle gave evidence of a "missed opportunity to consolidate the growth of an independent media in Russia" and the "failure of voters to obtain disinterested information from primary television outlets in a fragile democracy."⁸ Vatikiotis wrote: "Beyond mass communication various theoretical approaches on the media of communication, and their diverse applications, have evaluated their emancipatory role for either promoting participatory communication, or advancing the democratization of communication, or even encompassing

⁴ Examples are here: Rantanen, Terhi. *Foreign News in Imperial Russia: The Relationship between International and Russian News Agencies, 1856 – 1914*. Helsinki: Suomalainen Tiedeakatemia, 1990
Boyd-Barrett, Oliver. "Towards the "New Model" News Agencies". In: APA - Austria Presse Agentur (Ed.): *The Various Faces of Reality: Values in News (Agency) Journalism*. Innsbruck: Studien Verlag, 2002. Pp. 91-96

⁵ Peterson, Marvin W.; McLendon, Michael K. "The Press and State Policy Making for Higher Education." In: *The Review of Higher Education*. Vol. 22,3, Spring 1999. P. 223

⁶ Hughes, Sallie; Lawson, Chappell H. "Propaganda and Crony Capitalism: Partisan Bias in Mexican Television News". In: *Latin American Research Review*. Vol. 39, 3 (2004). P. 81

⁷ Hughes, Sallie; Lawson, Chappell H. "Propaganda and Crony Capitalism: Partisan Bias in Mexican Television News". In: *Latin American Research Review*. Vol. 39, 3 (2004). P. 81

⁸ Oates, Sarah; Roselle, Laura. "Russian Elections and TV News: Comparison of Campaign News on State-Controlled and Commercial Television Channels." In: *The Harvard International Journal of Press/Politics*. Vol. 5, 2, 2000. Pp. 30-51

modes of subversive action.”⁹ Globalization is here the process and mind concept connected with the work of internationally acting news agencies that enable the worldwide flow of news.¹⁰ We call public bodies *quangos* (quasi-autonomous nongovernmental organizations). These nongovernmental organizations have they own distributing media. Deacon and Monk examined mainstream news reporting for *quangos* and found “little endorsement in general media discourses about the quango state but is often implicitly reflected in journalists’ treatment of specific organizations and their work.”¹¹ We have to examine both the types of news agencies, their intern organization, their forms and formats of news presentation, and their relation to interest groups. Also the mediating role between the source of the news and the delivery of the news in the mass media is important.

GLOBAL CASES OF THE NETWORK OF NEWS AGENCIES THE NETWORK OF REUTERS BUSINESS – A CLASSIC NEWS AGENCY IN A BUSINESS ORGANIZATION AND ITS CUSTOMERS

Reuters is a classic example for a mass media conglomerate that is part of a broader business organization. According to the self-description of the company, Reuters acts through business divisions, geographic sales, and service channels and has shared resources to build, control, and support the products and services for their customers. These divisions and the user communities they serve are closely connected. The media division including the traditional wholesale agency business serves for the needs of international newspapers, television and cable networks, radio stations, websites, and consumers. The division also works on establishing a ‘new avenue of growth’ for Reuters through products designed specifically for consumers in the ‘Reuters.com family’ of various websites.¹² In other words: Reuters defines the user communities as the receivers of their services as a traditional wholesale agency business that includes news agency services. Reuters is a provider of international financial reports. Reuters Group is a financial market data provider and a news service that provides reports from around the world to newspapers and broadcasters.

⁹ Vatikiotis, Pantelis. Communication Theory and Alternative Media. Westminster University. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<[Http://www.wmin.ac.uk/mad/pdf/WPCC-Vol2-No1-Pantelis_Vatikiotis.pdf](http://www.wmin.ac.uk/mad/pdf/WPCC-Vol2-No1-Pantelis_Vatikiotis.pdf)>

¹⁰ Cf. As research on globalization and news media: Kunczik, Michael. Globalization: News Media, Images of Nations and the Flow of International Capital with Special Reference to the Role of Rating Agencies. Hamburg : Dt. Übersee-Institut, 2001

¹¹ Deacon, David and Monk, Wendy. “Executive Stressed: News Reporting of Quangos in Britain.” In: The Harvard International Journal of Press/Politics. Vol. 5, 3 (2000), Pp. 45

¹² About Reuters. Reuters. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<[Http://about.reuters.com/home/aboutus/ourcompany/companyorganisation.aspx](http://about.reuters.com/home/aboutus/ourcompany/companyorganisation.aspx)>

According to the *Reuters Trust Principles*, Reuters is interested in preserving its independence, integrity, and freedom from bias in the gathering and dissemination of news and information. The principles are beside 'independence', 'integrity', and 'freedom' for the news 'diversity' and 'growing expansion'. The *Reuters Trust Principles* state that Reuters "shall at no time pass into the hands of any one interest, group or faction", that the integrity, independence, and freedom from bias of Reuters "shall at all times be fully preserved", that Reuters "shall supply unbiased and reliable news services to newspapers, news agencies, broadcasters and other media subscribers and to businesses, governments, institutions, individuals and others with whom Reuters has or may have contracts", that Reuters "shall pay due regard to the many interests which it serves in addition to those of the media", and that "no effort shall be spared to expand, develop and adapt the news and other services and products of Reuters so as to maintain its leading position in the international news and information business."¹³ The customers of Reuters are besides mass media outlets organizations like business corporations and governmental organizations. Amateur journalism has developed especially on the internet many different formats. Among them are the blog, services for open source journalism, and specific format and topics of online journalism for non-professionals like citizen journalism. Established media conglomerates like Reuters intend to integrate the amateur journalism with specific formats in their program.

THE NETWORK OF ASSOCIATED PRESS (AP) – A NEWS AGENCY AS POOL AND DISTRIBUTOR FROM NEWSPAPERS TO NEWSPAPERS AND FROM NEWSPAPERS TO NEWS PORTALS

Associated Press (AP) is an example for the distribution of contents from news agencies to online news portals with the benefit of increasing presence of the agency as a source of daily news in the eye of the public audience. On the other hand the portals promote their services using news from news agencies. The news agency *Associated Press* sells the products in the formats AP News, AP Photos, AP Video, AP Audio, and AP Books. The *Associated Press* employs journalists with the ethic standards of fairness, balance, and accuracy in a network of more than 3,700 employees around the world. *Associated Press'* news reports cover international, national, state, sports, business, and entertainment news. *AP Exchange* is an online tool that offers newspaper editors and reporters access to *Associated Press'* pool of contents.¹⁴

¹³ About Reuters. Reuters.com. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<[Http://about.reuters.com/home/aboutus/ourcompany/independencetrust.aspx](http://about.reuters.com/home/aboutus/ourcompany/independencetrust.aspx)>

¹⁴ About Associated Press. Associated Press. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

Associated Press has the special sections Sending a Press Release, Beats, Editors and Writers, and New York Daybook.¹⁵ The *Associated Press* delivers news to web portals with news pages (Yahoo and MSN). Yahoo's news section gives the *Associated Press* visibility and is an advertisement of services of *Associated Press*. It has also an impact on *Associated Press'* public image. *Associated Press* as a U.S.-American news agency is the world's largest organization owned by its contributing newspapers, radio and television stations in the United States. These members contribute stories to it using material written by its staffers. Many newspapers and broadcasters outside the United States are subscribers of *Associated Press*. An elected board of directors from different cooperating U.S. newspapers governs the agency. *Associated Press* is an example for a circle of mass media information. Here the contributing newspapers produce the contents of the news agency use to be distributed to the other members.

Meta-news-portals are Google News, Indymedia, and Wikinews. The portal YAHOO NEWS covers different sections of news from different news agencies. The following agencies cover the sections (October 18, 2007):

Besides YAHOO! NEWS YAHOO! offers specific news in several sections. On the contrary, Google News doesn't employ any special service on their homepage dedicated to the latest news. Google News is a separated service that relies directly on several hundred news media sources presented in several national and international sections based on logarithmic selection. Google has the features News Archive Search, Advanced News Search, and Blog Search.

World	Business	Science
U.S. News	Reuters	AP
Politics	AFP	Reuters
AP Reuters AFP	BusinessWeek	AFP
Time.com NPR	FT.com	SPACE.com
My	NPR	LiveScience.com
Sources	USATODAY.com	NPR
AP	FOX News	
Reuters		
AFP		
Time.com		
NPR		
Technology	Health	Entertainment
AP	AP	AP
Reuters	Reuters	Reuters

<[Http://www.ap.org/pages/about/about.html](http://www.ap.org/pages/about/about.html)>

¹⁵ Blue Page. Associated Press. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<[Http://hosted.ap.org/specials/bluepage.html#ca](http://hosted.ap.org/specials/bluepage.html#ca)>

USATODAY.com	HealthDay	AFP
PC World	AFP	E! Online
PC Magazine	NPR	Fashion Wire Daily
AFP	ACS News Today	NPR
Travel	Sports	Odd News
AP	AP	Reuters
TSA	Reuters	AP
AP Features	The Sporting News	Reuters UK
	AFP	AFP
		Opinion
		USATODAY.com
		CSMonitor.com
		RealClearPolitics
		HuffingtonPost.com

Coverage of Sections of YAHOO NEWS by News Agencies

Yahoo! Finance	Top Stories
Yahoo! Sports	World
Yahoo! Health	U.S.
Yahoo!	Business
Entertainment	Sci/Tech
Yahoo! TV	Sports
Yahoo! Movies	Entertainment
	Health
	News Alerts
	News Sections of Google News

Specific News Sections of YAHOO!
News

News Sections of the News Portal Yahoo and Google News

Both Yahoo and Google have international versions. The placement of stories on this page is selected automatically by a computer program.¹⁶

AHN AS A GLOBAL NEWS AGENCY NETWORK - INTEGRATING THE CONSUMER IN THE NEWS PRODUCTION

¹⁶ Google News. Google. Retrieved October 18, 2007.

<Http://news.google.com/>

AHN is a global news agency and content service with offices and regional bureaus in South Florida, New York, Washington, D.C., Las Vegas, Denver, and Europe and Asia providing breaking news and content 24 hours a day, 365 days a year. The company describes itself as a provider of news, weather, and other content for web sites, wireless services, digital signage networks, interactive applications, broadcasting, and print media. The company's content services are available worldwide by web sites, newspapers, digital signage networks, TV/Radio stations, magazines, portals, websites, charities, governmental entities, educational institutions, and other organizations. The core competency is "to generate, aggregate and syndicate dynamic news content and information to customers in an easy to use format. AHN continues to refine and develop products and outlets that will provide publishers, webmasters and advertisers access to the best in news and content services on the internet."¹⁷ AHN delivers news and contents in several formats. For portals and websites AHN offers integrated news, weather, horoscopes, and other contents. For Digital signage networks it offers news and content delivered by automated feed. For print and newspapers it offers breaking full text news stories. Traditionally, one of the sources of news agencies are organizations and their related public relations agencies, but with the possibilities of amateur news production many news agencies have the chances to a) add information and news not available at other places and b) to have an increasing attraction for readers as interactive participants. AHN is open for a public audience to deliver news. Besides professional organizations, PR and news agencies as well as amateurs and other groups or individual people can send their information. One of the *News Submission Terms and Conditions* for contributions to AHN states: "AHN reserves the right not to use the material you submit at all and/or as little of the material as it chooses."¹⁸

NETWORKS OF INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS – NEWS AGENCIES ORGANIZED IN NATIONAL FEDERATIONS AND PRESENTED BY LOBBIES

We will now examine one of the national news agencies selecting its specific offers of contents. The *Bulgarian News Agency* (BTA) is an example for the network of a national news agency connected as a common federation to other news agencies and major commercial news agencies. Besides the American continent many European and Asian news agencies are organized in federations. On the contrary, in the U.S. the major agencies are participants in a commercial competition on the market often joint with other businesses in a

¹⁷ Website AHN Media Corporation. Allheadlinenews. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<Http://www.allheadlinenews.com/corp/>

¹⁸ Website AHN Media Corporation. Allheadlinenews. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<Http://www.allheadlinenews.com/corp/>

company. For Arab counties one example is the *Federation of Arab News Agencies* (FANA). Other federations are the *Association of Balkan News Agencies* (ABNA), the *Alliance of Mediterranean News Agencies* (AMAN), the *European Alliance of News Agencies* (EANA), and the *Organization of Asia-Pacific News Agencies*. The *European Alliance of News Agencies* EANA has 30 member agencies.

The *Bulgarian News Agency* (BTA) is Bulgaria's national state news agency and deals with Bulgaria related contents both commercially and free for its customers. A decree issued by Prince Ferdinand I in 1898 established it. The BTA is a major source of information for print and electronic media, the state bodies, and NGOs in Bulgaria. A statute adopted by the 36th National Assembly on 29 June 1994 regulates BTA's operations. The agency is 'an autonomous national news organization'. BTA has the following sections:

News	Weather Today
(Free News Stories)	Currency Exchange
Original Texts	Rates
Bulgaria	Bulgarian Institutions
The Balkans	President
Today's Special	Parliament
Press Review	Government
	Constitutional Court
Original Texts Services	Archive
(OTS)	
E-Clipping	

Sections of the Bulgarian News Agency (BTA)

BTA finances its operations from the sale of its information services and products through advertisements and action allocations from the national budget. BTA is a member of the *European Alliance of News Agencies*, whose statute stipulates that only one news agency per country can participate. BTA is also a member of the *Association of Balkan News Agencies*. BTA exchanges information with national agencies.¹⁹ BTA's economic news and analysis service is also available for U.S. agencies such as Factiva, Dow Jones, Reuters, and the Internet Securities Inc. services. BTA receives and sends to its subscribers products of the picture services of the *European Pressphoto Agency* (EPA) and *Associated Press*.²⁰

¹⁹ Official Website of Bulgarian News Agency. BTA. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<[Http://www.bta.bg/site/en/indexe.shtml](http://www.bta.bg/site/en/indexe.shtml)>

²⁰ About Us. Bulgarian News Agency. BTA. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

News Agencies as Institutions for Covering Special Interest Groups

Certain news agencies cover news of special interest groups, but also declare themselves as an active part of a group with a specific interest or act as PR agencies for a specific interest. A local example in England for the merge of news agencies and PR is *Newsflash Press Agency*, a press and picture agency specializing in news, features, pictures, and corporate work. Also *North News and Pictures* is a specialized agency for news, pictures, and PR photography.²¹ *Inter Press Service* (IPS) is an example for a news service with declared political, educational, and economical interests. *Inter Press Service* (IPS) declares itself as an “independent voice from the South and for development, delving into globalization for the stories underneath.”²² IPS’s motto is “Another communication is possible.”²³ The core business of the IPS news agency is reporting and analysis of events and global processes “affecting the economic, social and political development of peoples and nations, especially in the South.”²⁴ IPS carries out communication projects and programs that are relevant to this core business and support the overall mission of IPS. Besides the news coverage IPS participates in projects and programs on international, regional, and sub-regional level involving other partners from media and civil society. According to its *Editorial Policy* IPS treats all news events “as part of a process rather than as isolated phenomena.”²⁵ Its *Editorial Policy* declares as an aim the promotion of a minority, ‘people excluded or marginalized by the process of globalization’:

“Reporting events without seeking to understand cause and effect means that readers will not have enough information to fully understand the world around them. The service does not

[Http://www.bta.bg/site/en/html/01aboutus.htm](http://www.bta.bg/site/en/html/01aboutus.htm)

²¹ Official Website of Newsflash Press Agency. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<[Http://www.newsflashscotland.com](http://www.newsflashscotland.com)>

Official Website of North News and Pictures. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<[Http://www.northnews.co.uk/home/](http://www.northnews.co.uk/home/)>

²² Official Website of IPS Inter Press Service. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<[Http://www.ips.org/](http://www.ips.org/)>

²³ Official Website of IPS Inter Press Service. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<[Http://www.ips.org/](http://www.ips.org/)>

²⁴ Official Website of IPS Inter Press Service. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<[Http://www.ips.org/](http://www.ips.org/)>

²⁵ Official Website of IPS Inter Press Service. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<[Http://www.ips.org/](http://www.ips.org/)>

aim to provide up-to-the minute coverage of events, as is the style of traditional news agencies.”²⁶

The IPS network with its headquarters in Rome and five editorial desks in Montevideo for Latin America, London-Berlin for Europe and the Mediterranean, Bangkok for Asia and the Pacific, Montreal for North America and the Caribbean, and Johannesburg for Africa operates globally. IPS has a network of more than 300 journalists around the world.²⁷ Critical reporting, local reports, and entertainment are special fields of journalism that are also covered by specialized news agencies. Regarding its presentation contents of *United Press International* (UPI) must be separated from standard news agencies dedicated to hard news as a provider of ‘critical information’ for media outlets, businesses, governments, and researchers worldwide. For a special need *Quirky News*, a British agency, sells users contents about all things ‘odd, weird and strange’ to newspapers, magazines, and TV companies.²⁸ *Afrol News African News Agency* describes itself as the only independent news agency dedicated only to Africa. *Afrol News African News Agency* deals with specific news from Africa selected into sections regions and topics. Not only news of specific interest groups or lobbies are received as news from the news agencies transmitting and publishing their news; vice versa organizations use the presentation of public news agencies representing their members. This is a method similar to the practice of distributing contents of news agencies for new portals. Conversely, news agencies can be used as tools for presenting a special interest group. Also organizations can form and promote news agencies according to the needs of the public audience and for their intern use. An example are member countries of the *OPEC* linked to their national news agencies to promote published material about member states on the *OPEC* homepage.²⁹ In such a presentation a common identity is at least as the website presentation produced.

NETWORKS OF ALTERNATIVE MEDIA, OPEN SOURCE NEWS, AND META-NEWS-PORTALS ALTERNATIVE MEDIA - NEWS NETWORKS AND OPEN SOURCE NETWORKS

²⁶ Official Website of Quirky News. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<[Http://www.quirkynews.co.uk](http://www.quirkynews.co.uk)>

²⁷ Official Website of IPS. Inter Press Service. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<[Http://www.pressalliance.com/news.htm](http://www.pressalliance.com/news.htm)>

²⁸ Official Website of Quirky News. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<[Http://www.quirkynews.co.uk](http://www.quirkynews.co.uk)>

²⁹ Official Website of the Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC). Retrieved September 22, 2007.

<[Http://www.opec.org/home/links/Na_links.htm](http://www.opec.org/home/links/Na_links.htm)>

In the following cases mass media organizations (1) operate without any external news agency or news network (Wikinews) based upon news exclusively written for Wikinews or (2) serve both as a news agency and a forum for news presentation (*Mathaba News Network*). Placed outside the circle of the mass media not contributing to the mass media news circulation, we can describe them as alternative media, even though their forms and presentation is identical with the one of the mainstream media. Alternative media are most broadly defined as media practices falling outside the mainstream of corporate communication of mainstream media. Chomsky proposed in his propaganda model a concrete model for the filtering processes of biases in mainstream media in the United States. According to the 'agenda-setting theory' the news media preorganize the contents of the consumers. Here of course the news agencies as the first selective institutions for contents of mass media function as important decision makers. Especially for news from distant places the agencies share news, while staff of local newspapers cover local news. In alternative media this preselection is low and the technical conditions of the organization are framing conditions for contributions. Chomsky separated media types as sectors: "There is another sector of the media, the elite media, sometimes called the agenda-setting media because they are the ones with the big resources, they set the framework in which everyone else operates. The New York Times and CBS, that kind of thing. Their audience is mostly privileged people. [...] They are basically managers of one sort or another. They can be political managers, business managers (like corporate executives or that sort of thing), doctoral managers (like university professors), or other journalists who are involved in organizing the way people think and look at things."³⁰ *Mathaba News Network* is a news agency and an online news network. The agency presents articles contributed by authors, correspondents and analysts as well as by members, 'mathabas', and by agreement. Politically it is an opponent of globalism and present-day world order. Mathaba's aim is "to bring news and information to the public free-of-charge" and "to assist in effecting better understanding and positive development".³¹ The method is amateur journalism by "an individual who has something to say or report, first gathers around him or her at least two others who agree. This already means there is a public interest potential. They form themselves thus into a (spontaneous) 'Mathaba' (meeting platform, circle, center) and work collectively to submit the news and information that should reach the suitable audience by publication."³² On October 18th,

³⁰ Chomsky, Noam. What Makes Mainstream Media Mainstream. Z Magazine. October, 1997. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<<http://www.chomsky.info/articles/199710--.htm>>

³¹ Official Website Mathaba News. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<[Http://www.mathaba.net/add/](http://www.mathaba.net/add/)>

³² Official Website Mathaba News. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<[Http://www.mathaba.net/add/](http://www.mathaba.net/add/)>

2007 *Mathaba News* had 4,100 reactions from bloggers.³³ *Mathaba News* allows users to submit contents in the formats *Direct Input, Commercial, PR, or Publicity*. In *Print Top Ten Ideas of '04: Open Source Journalism, Or "My Readers Know More Than I Do"* Jay Rosen stated: "The audience always knew more, but it didn't have a network for pulling its scattered self together. An atomized public needed the journalist to know for it. That's how we got a professionalized press. [...] Open Source journalism builds on that insight. When you talk about the Web era in journalism think: audience atomization overcome.

Then you will be on the right track."³⁴ Wikinews is a free online news portal based on the principles of open source journalism. Following Wikipedia "open source is a set of principles and practices that promote access to the design and production of goods and knowledge."³⁵ For Wikinews "the open source model of operation can be extended to open source culture in decision making, which allows concurrent input of different agendas, approaches and priorities, in contrast with more centralized models of development such as those typically used in commercial companies."³⁶ The Wikimedia project describes itself as follows: "We are a group of volunteers whose mission is to present reliable, unbiased, relevant and entertaining News."³⁷ Wikinews doesn't separate between national and international news in its sections focusing on local news. It has on the contrary a global audience and uses different world languages.

<i>Home</i>	<i>Crime and Law</i>
<i>World</i>	<i>Culture</i> and
<i>Revo</i>	<i>Entertainment</i>
<i>Issues</i>	<i>Disasters and Accidents</i>
<i>Culture/Edu</i>	<i>Economy and Business</i>
<i>Life/Health</i>	<i>Education</i>
<i>Entertainment</i>	<i>Environment</i>
<i>Sci/Tech</i>	<i>Health</i>
<i>Business</i>	<i>Obituaries</i>

³³ Official Website Mathaba News. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<Http://www.mathaba.net/add/>

³⁴ Rosen, Jay. *Print Top Ten Ideas of '04: Open Source Journalism, Or "My Readers Know More Than I Do."* PressThink Blog. Harvard University. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<Http://blogs.law.harvard.edu/mediaberkman/2006/11/14/jay-rosen-on-open-source-journalism/>

³⁵ Wikipedia. Open Source. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<Http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_source>

³⁶ Wikipedia. Open Source. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<Http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_source>

³⁷ Wikinews. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<Http://en.wikinews.org/wiki/Main_Page>

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Alternative Media: Open Source News Agency and News Portal

CONCLUSIONS - RECENT SWIFTS IN THE LANDSCAPE OF NEWS AGENCIES

Recent research described news agencies as an element for the ‘flow of news.’³⁸ For Volkmer in *International Communication Theory in Transition: Parameters of the New Global Public Sphere* the terms ‘international,’ ‘transnational,’ and ‘global’ communication not only “stand for different definitions of an expanding communication space”, but also “reflect the history of worldwide communication as well as its diversity.”³⁹ Global communication gives us an “eyewitness view of events in remotest locations, we participate in political discourses of global, regional or even local relevance.”⁴⁰ Adapted to the classical communication model of Shannon, news agencies have a mediating role between the source of the news sending the news and its receiver, an audience of the specific news outlet consuming this information. Theoretically in this position is can select, adapt, and change the flow and contents of the whole information or parts of the news it transfers. Connectivity, distribution, and flow of information are features associated with networks integrating news agencies as ‘media for the mass media’. Besides communicative features such as

³⁸ Cf.: Pinch, Edward T. “The Flow of News: An Assessment of the Non-Aligned News Agencies Pool”. In: *Journal of Communication*. Vol. 28, 4 (1978). Pp 163-175

Ivacic, Pero. “The Flow of News: Tanjug, the Pool, and the National Agencies.” In: *Journal of Communication*. Vol. 28, 4 (1978) Pp. 157-170

An example for a synchronic study is: Wu, HD. “Systemic Determinants of International News Coverage: A Comparison of 38 Countries”. In: *Journal of Communication*. Volume 50, Issue 2, Jun 2000, Pp. 110-130

³⁹ Volkmer, Ingrid. *International Communication Theory in Transition: Parameters of the New Global Public Sphere*. MIT. Retrieved June 26, 2007.
<[Http://web.mit.edu/comm-forum/papers/volkmer.html](http://web.mit.edu/comm-forum/papers/volkmer.html)>

⁴⁰ Volkmer, Ingrid. *International Communication Theory in Transition: Parameters of the New Global Public Sphere*. MIT. Retrieved June 26, 2007.
<[Http://web.mit.edu/comm-forum/papers/volkmer.html](http://web.mit.edu/comm-forum/papers/volkmer.html)>

functions as nodes and a fast exchange of the information in mass communication the connection of the producers and senders of information is important. Traditionally, in media studies the term ‘framing’ refers to a process of selective influence over the individual's view of the meanings of information. The mass media or specific political or social movements or organizations may set up media frames. Another effect associated with framing are prestructured forms and types for the delivery of news prior to their arrival at a concrete place for delivery to the consumer. Here the news agencies have an important role, since they operate globally and with a coverage beyond the local coverage of news. The news agencies as providers of information for the final outlets of news include framing to select news and the contents of news. News agencies as part of an international information flow are communicative entities with the potential power to vary the news with the selection and presentation. In recent years the structure of the media world with their organization has changed; we find classic forms of news providers like news agencies connected with other types of providers and even organizations that can be classified as a part of the public relations business. The internet has an extreme influence on news. It increases in general an immediate availability of news all over the world for various kinds of news outlets.

Conglomerate

The isolated news agency that works independently is rare. Most news agencies participate either as a section of a business conglomerate with other branches (Reuters) or in a media conglomerate, a state, or as a section of an interest group in business conglomerates. In the last case they operate like PR agencies.

Globalization

Ivacic argued “current efforts to build a new international economic order inevitably stimulated initiatives for change in the structure of information, which for decades had been based on a one-way flow of news from the developed to the developing countries under the influence of a small number of news agency giants in the developed world.”⁴¹ The internet increases the sum of news with immediate availability all over the world for various kinds of news outlets. If we ask for the globality of news agencies, we can answer this question in the following way using features for a global network:

Globalization as feature of the sources and coverage of the news

Globalization as feature of delivering the news

Globalization as feature of the interconnectivity of the agency with other networks

⁴¹ Ivacic, Pero. The Non-aligned Countries Pool Their News - News Agency Network. UNESCO Courier, May-June, 1986. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<http://findarticles.com/p/articles/mi_m1310/is_1986_May-June/ai_4375051>

Interactivity and Intermediality

Interactivity and intermediality are phenomena that have recently produced forms of news presentation like blogs for the contribution of readers and other people and groups of amateurs with a specific knowledge. Here also the interference between professional and nonprofessional journalism is obvious. All of these forms are available for both groups. News agencies are bound to other organizations or corporations. In other words: They operate as a part of an organization. When examining the contemporary news landscape and mass media as an area of communications, we must be aware of the fact that news are distributed in certain circles of media organizations. Figuratively spoken, as long as it is not channeled and forwarded in the mass media, news is not news. The effect of imbalance due to lack of information in several groups and the dominance of other groups was coined as 'spiral of silence' by Noelle-Neumann.⁴² Rantanen argued that news agencies played a key role in globalization, using the early submarine cable networks in the latter half of the 19th century.⁴³ For Rantanen manipulation of time and space on a global scale was "an essential component in the construction of news as a category and in its commodification."⁴⁴ A result is that "distances make news as news available."⁴⁵ Ivacic stated that "news exchange, the basis of relations among news agencies, is more important today than ever before."⁴⁶ In recent years, news exchange has become "accepted practice for most news agencies in the nonaligned world. January 1977 marked the second anniversary of the creation of the system known as the 'pool' - a multichannel flow of news reports and information "between agencies of nonaligned countries."⁴⁷ Framing is the placement of news of one specific topic taken from and delivered to a specific interest group. Here news agencies have important positions regarding the preselection of news distributed to the mass media. Lind and Salo demonstrated that framing of feminists and feminism in news and public affairs

⁴² Noelle-Neumann, Elisabeth. "The Spiral of Silence. A Theory of Public Opinion". In: Journal of Communication. Vol. 24, 2. 1974, Pp. 43-51

Simpson, Christopher. "Elisabeth Noelle-Neumann's 'Spiral of Silence' and the Historical Context of Communication Theory." In: Journal of Communication, Vol. 46,3, 1996, Pp. 149-171

⁴³Rantanen, Terhi. "The Globalization of Electronic News in the 19th Century." In: Media, Culture & Society. Vol. 19, 4. 1997, Pp. 605

⁴⁴Rantanen, Terhi. "The Globalization of Electronic News in the 19th Century." In: Media, Culture & Society. Vol. 19, 4. 1997, Pp. 605

⁴⁵Rantanen, Terhi. "The Globalization of Electronic News in the 19th Century." In: Media, Culture & Society. Vol. 19, 4. 1997, Pp. 605

⁴⁶ Ivacic, Pero. The Non-aligned Countries Pool Their News - News Agency Network. UNESCO Courier, May-June, 1986. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<http://findarticles.com/p/articles/mi_m1310/is_1986_May-June/ai_4375051>

⁴⁷ Ivacic, Pero. The Non-aligned Countries Pool Their News - News Agency Network. UNESCO Courier, May-June, 1986. Retrieved June 26, 2007.

<http://findarticles.com/p/articles/mi_m1310/is_1986_May-June/ai_4375051>

programs in U.S. electronic media serves as an example of controlled and planned news distribution.⁴⁸ The network is the specific set of connections an agency has to spread news. The framework is the surrounding structure of a news agency that sets up its conditions for the delivery of news. One of the functions of news agencies we can describe as ‘framing of the news flow’. This means that the news flow comes from specific directions to the news agency and leaves the news agency again in specific directions for distribution. News distributed by the news agencies have formats framed by the background of their interest groups. Framing comprises here both selection and design of contents. Serving as frames news agencies decide regarding the form, contents, structure, and availability of news in a preselection process. In the ‘news flow’ (the movement of the news from the source to the final media outlet in several steps) information of the news is subject to changes and editorial decisions. The ‘news flow’ can be direct or indirect.

News Flow From The News to the News Outlet. Linear Chain Distribution

New types of news agencies influence the classic role of a news agency with a selected spectrum of news serving a selected audience and selected interest groups. Another type of news agency serves just a specific group of mass media with news related to a specific interest (e.g. ‘humor’/‘entertainment’).

Organizing news agencies as a distributor of news can result in the selection of groups able to transfer their news. Here only organizations in the distribution circle can participate, while others are subject to the ‘spiral of silence’-phenomenon. In *Spirals of Silence: The Dynamic Effects of Diversity on*

⁴⁸ Cf.: Lind, Rebecca Ann and Colleen Salo. “The Framing of Feminists and Feminism in News and Public Affairs Programs in U.S. Electronic Media.” In: Journal of Communication. Vol. 52, 1, 2002, Pp. 211

Organizational Voice Noelle-Neumann’s theory was applied to management.⁴⁹ Bowen and Blackmon mentioned that Noelle-Neumann's spiral of silence “emphasizes the horizontal pressures that the threat of isolation and corresponding fear of isolation exert to keep people from being open and honest about their opinions.”⁵⁰

⁴⁹ Kerckhove, Derrick de. “McLuhan and the ‘Toronto School of Communication’”. Originally published in: *Canadian Journal of Communication* (1989). Pp. 73-79. The McLuhan Program in Culture and Technology. University Toronto. Retrieved September 22, 2007.

<[Http://www.utoronto.ca/mcluhan/article_torontoschoolofcomm.htm](http://www.utoronto.ca/mcluhan/article_torontoschoolofcomm.htm)>

⁵⁰ Bowen, Frances and Kate Blackmon. “Spirals of Silence: The Dynamic Effects of Diversity on Organizational Voice”. In: *Journal of Management Studies*. Vol.40, 6. 2003, Pp. 1393-1417

News Flow to News Agencies. Linear Chain Distribution

Information News Flow in Mass Media. Circulating Distribution

In the news flow of a circulating distribution the news circulates from one media to other media. The difference between the linear form of chain distribution and the circulating distribution is that in the second case the news is reduplicated and placed in other formats, while the first case is mainly a production process. Global network news agencies comprise various globally working agencies including specific functions such as *Mathaba News Agency*, national agencies like *Agence France-Presse*, *ANTARA News*, an Indonesian News Portal, or *AP Digital*, a global news network. A news agency for a special interest group is *KNA*, the *Catholic News Agency*, globally covering news of the Catholic church.⁵¹ We can distinguish between the following types of news agencies:

- News agencies as independent news organizations
- News agencies as depending organizations
- State owned news agencies
- Company owned news agencies
- News agencies owned by organizations (NGOs)

⁵¹ Official website KNA. Katholische Nachrichten-Agentur. Retrieved June 26, 2007. <Http://www.kna.de>

'New Media' and Internet News Agencies News Agencies in Mass Media Conglomerates

When the distance between the news agency and the aims of the organization behind it is too small and diversity lacks, the news agency fulfills functions of a PR agency. We demonstrate that news agencies work independently in a limited linear form (chain model). In a second way distributed news circulated (circulation model). Related to this effect is Noelle-Neumann's idea of the 'spiral of silence' as retroactive tendency to describe the lack of information by selection. A tendency of interference between journalism, PR, and marketing results in the questioning for the independence of their actions. Since many news agencies don't have a closed organizational structure as homogenous organizations, it is also necessary to re-examine them also as business corporations in the mass media industry. In a theoretical model, news agencies are embedded in the mass media industry.

National news agencies are responsible for distributing local, regional, and international news services for local and international media organizations. For mass communication, news agencies comprise the basic areas of message production and message processing. Discourse and interaction depend on their specific structure for access to an audience. News agencies help developing relationships between consumers (readers) and producers (outlets) supporting them. News agencies can also share the interests of small groups and special interest groups. Regarding contents, formats, and language the presentation of the news depends on the needs of specific society and culture or global features.